

The calculated values of activation energy from Arrhenius plot (Fig. 1) are presented in Table 4.

TABLE 4—VALUES OF ACTIVATION ENERGIES FOR INITIAL STAGE OF DEHYDRATION

Hydrogel	Size fraction	Activation energy kcal mol ⁻¹
• Silicic acid	-20+50	5.95
	-50+80	6.18
	-80+115	5.95
	-115+150	6.17
	-150+200	5.72
	-200+300	6.17

The activation energy values clearly demonstrate the absence of any effect of particle size. Thus no positive effect of particle size was observed on the kinetics of dehydration.

The results of the present study show that (i) particle size has practically no influence on the dehydration rates, (ii) with decrease in particle size, the extent of linearity increased only to a small extent and (iii) no positive effect of particle size was observed on the kinetics of dehydration.

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Effect of Addition of D(+) Glucose on the B-Z Oscillating Reaction

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BELOUSOV-Zhabotinsky^{1,2} oscillating reaction has been well studied³⁻⁶ for the last few years.

In this communication, the effect of addition of D(+)-glucose, a typical reducing agent, on this reaction has been studied in the presence and absence of it. Gallic acid⁷⁻⁹ and citric acid² have been used as organic substrates and in both the systems, the changes in induction period, time period *etc.* on addition of glucose have been studied in details. Attempts have been made to explain the experimental results in terms of Field, Körös and Noyes (FKN) mechanism¹⁰.

Experimental

In the reaction with citric acid, solid glucose was taken in the reaction vessel. Separate solutions of ceric ammonium sulphate, potassium bromate and citric acid were prepared in sulphuric acid. Ferroin was used as an indicator and the reaction was triggered by the addition of citric acid solution. In case of gallic acid system, solid gallic acid was taken in the reaction vessel and solutions of sulphuric acid, glucose and potassium bromate were added. Here also ferroin was used as an indicator. Use of Ce^{IV} ions was however, unnecessary in this case and the reaction was triggered by the addition of bromate solution.

All solutions were so prepared and mixed that the concentrations in Tables 1 and 2 refer to the concentrations in media. In both cases the reaction mixture was stirred at a fixed rate. The sharp colour changes, blue to green in the case of citric acid, and red to light green in the case of gallic acid were utilised for recording induction period (appearance of first green colour), time period of oscillation, total number of oscillations and total time of oscillation. The experimental results have been summarised in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF D(+)-GLUCOSE ON B-Z SYSTEM CONTAINING GALLIC ACID AT 32°

[KBrO₃] = 0.1008 M, [H₂SO₄] = 1.1062 M, [gallic acid] = 0.0399 M, [ferroin] ≈ 0.0003 M

[D(+)-glucose] M	Induction period sec	Average of 3rd and 4th oscillation periods sec	Total no. of oscillations	Total time of oscillations sec
0.0948	94	7	4	25
0.0758	99	5	6	37
0.0472	123	6.5	9	78
0.0190	155	11	19	371
0.0095	146	17	44	1247
nil	156	20	82	2799

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF D(+)-GLUCOSE ON B-Z SYSTEM CONTAINING CITRIC ACID AT 29°

[KBrO₃] = 0.0153 M, [H₂SO₄] = 1.54 M, [citric acid] = 0.457 M, [ferroin] = 0.0007 M, [Ce^{IV}] = 0.0037 M

[D(+)-glucose] M	Induction period sec	Average of 3rd and 4th oscillation periods sec
0.0580	46	34.5
0.0390	62	42
0.0166	66	58
nil	71	93

Results and Discussion

The experimental results reveal that with both citric and gallic acid the induction period and the oscillation period decrease with increasing concentrations of glucose. For oscillation period, the average of 3rd and 4th oscillation periods has been considered as the first one or two oscillations are anomalous in many systems. In the case of gallic

acid, total number of oscillations and total time of oscillation have also been recorded and these were also found to decrease as the concentration of glucose was increased. Again as no reactant was added during the progress of the reaction, the reaction systems were closed in the thermodynamic sense and the general increase in time period with time in gallic acid system is in conformity with expectations. In case of citric acid, although the first oscillation periods at some glucose concentrations are rather abnormal, the periods in general do not change with time as in the case of sustained oscillations.

The effect of glucose on B-Z reaction can be explained in the light of the FKN mechanism, which involves 3 intermediates, the control intermediate, i.e. Br⁻, the switched intermediate, i.e. bromous acid, and the regeneration intermediate, i.e. Fe^{III}, Ce^{IV} ions etc. The following are the probable¹¹ reactions in gallic acid system.

Process A: Reaction of bromide with bromate ion to yield bromine. This last species undergoes fast reaction with gallic acid to generate bromogallic acid (BrHG).

Process B: Autocatalytic formation of bromous acid with a rapid oxidation of Fe²⁺ to Fe³⁺.

This process is important only when Br⁻ is under a critical value, bromide ion being an inhibitor of process B by step A2. There is an autocatalytic production of HBrO₂ limited by its dismutation in step B2. In the process B, there is a very rapid accumulation of Fe³⁺.

Process C: A recovery process.

This process is the Fe³⁺ oxidation of organic brominated species and generates a bromide ion, thus switching back the reaction to the process A.

As the process A proceeds, the process C continues to deplete Fe³⁺ from the reaction mixture, enabling the bromide concentration to undergo the critical value below which the process B can be switched again.

The reducing property of glucose is perhaps responsible for the decrease of induction period as well as oscillation period. It competes with gallic acid for bromine¹² (or other bromine species in higher oxidation states) as a result of which Br₂ is

quickly consumed and process A takes place quickly. It also controls the formation of Br⁻ because bromogallic acid, which is the chief regenerator of Br⁻ through process C is formed in smaller amount in its presence. As a result, process B (which is significant at low Br⁻ concentration) starts sooner. The net result is that the induction period is decreased, oscillation starts sooner and the oscillations are quickly completed decreasing the oscillation period. The total number of oscillations as also the total time of oscillation decrease as bromate is consumed more in each cycle in presence of glucose. As the concentration of glucose is increased, all of these values decrease. It is likely that in citric acid system a similar mechanism is operative.

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Synthesis and Fungicidal Activity of Some Mixed 5-Pyrazolone and 5-Thiopyrazolone Derivatives

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IT has been observed from our earlier work on heterocyclic fungicides¹⁻⁵ that 5-pyrazonones possess significant fungicidal activity against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* and the brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae*. The survey of literature further reveals that thiopyrazo-

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